

THE NEW MEDIA MONOPOLY: A CASE STUDY OF NEW MEDIA DISRUPTION IN SEEKING THE CONSUMER MARKET OF TRIBUN TIMUR AND HARIAN FAJAR READERS IN MAKASSAR CITY

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Abstract:

The revolution in the field of science and technology has made the mass media have such a broad spectrum, reaching all regions, and layers of society with massive intensity. The role of media as social control is also evident. Print media is able to absorb thousands of workers, an industry that provides information consumption to the public, and is one of the pillars of democracy in a country. However, the greatness of the print media gradually began to be rivaled by increasingly sophisticated electronic media. This article aims to find out how New Media in capturing the consumer market for the readers of the Harian Fajar & Tribun Timur newspapers in Makassar City. This study uses a qualitative-exploratory method with a comparative case study approach to answering the steps of Fajar & Tribun Timur Daily in seizing the consumer market for newspaper readers in the era of New Media. The results of this study indicate that Fajar Daily & Tribun Timur Daily do not need a relatively long time to exist in the midst of the current development of online media. Tribun Timur & Fajar Daily have anticipated this by publishing Tribun-Timur.com & Fajar.com, the online version. Mainstream Media Readers of these two print media have partially turned to online news. But at the end of 2019, there was another big change. Facebook and YouTube and Instagram are new references for news and information seekers. This has been exacerbated by the Covid-19 pandemic. So that the transformation of mainstream media such as Tribun Timur & Harin Fajar also needs to transform to social media.

Keywords: New Media Technology, Era of Media Disruption, Media Strategy, Media Market Competition, Harian Fajar, Harian Tribun Timur.

Introduction

The mass media, as the mainstream media, actually has to straighten out what is crooked and does not dissolve in unverified news (Juditha, C., 2018; Kominfo, 2018). The main media must be smart to face the onslaught of social digital media. Between social media and mainstream media have their respective advantages. Social media stands out for its speed, while mainstream media stands out for its accuracy and depth of material (Nurliah, 2018; Rosidah, 2017). Social media is used by almost all smartphone users, whether the general public to state officials. The digitalization of communication media has made every individual a news producer. This has become a new fad among the people, now everyone is playing on social media, regents, mayors, governors, ministers, to the president. Everyone plays social media, some like Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, Path. Everyone is obsessed with social media (Rosidah, 2017).

The development of mass media in Indonesia does not forget the role of mass media conglomerate groups as mainstream media/mainstream media, which persists in the era of disruption of new media technology. They make the print media stable first—and usually

have a strong non-print business too. Such as the news of James Riady's Satu Media Holding, Dahlan Iskan's Jawa Pos, and Jakoeb Oetama's Kompas Gramedia (Adam, A., 2018). The media business industry runs a different paradigm according to the development of the time (Tapsell, R. 2017). In the digital era, we are entering the era of media convergence, where in this converged world, everything can be recorded in a new media chain that can be connected to each other. This wide selection of mediums makes today's mass media able to speak in a variety of different ways. Even though the content is the same, mass media can take a different approach in each platform it uses. Circulation of media content through different platforms challenges information consumers to seek out new information and connect content presented through these various platforms (Jenkins, 2006; Christensen, 2006).

New media disruption is not only a technical instrument to create illusions, but new media is also a new language that has a unique power of expression (McLuhan, M., 1960; Lenggawa, 2018). Newspapers that still adhere to the principles of journalistic work based on the code of ethics and Law no. 40 of 1999, has the power to balance the freedom of information and the rise of hoax news. Kominfo data (2017) released in 2017 states that there are around 800,000 sites in Indonesia that have been indicated as spreading false information. Meanwhile, internet users in Indonesia have reached around 132.7 million people (Kominfo, 2018; Nugroho, B. & Samsuri, 2013).

From the research notes above regarding the rise of hoaxes on social media platforms, public trust in social media and search engines has decreased. In a report published by "databoks.com" entitled the 2018 Edelman Trust Barometer Global Report, the level of public trust in social media platforms fell 2 percentage points to 51% compared to the previous year of 53%. Meanwhile, public trust in mainstream media journalists and trustworthy online media in 2018 actually increased 5 percentage points to 59% from the previous 54%. It is stated that the public is getting tired of the massive amount of fake news milling about in their media accounts and prefers to seek news and information from reliable media (Juditha, 2018; Tarigan, 2017). The emergence of fake/fake news does not only hit developing countries such as Indonesia and other Asian countries but also occurs in developed countries such as the United States. Donald Trump's victory in the United States general election has triggered an increase in hoaxes in a country that has a level of education and technology that is more advanced than Indonesia (Juditha, 2018; Tarigan, 2017).

The rise of hoaxes has made the mainstream media/mainstream media the public's hope for obtaining accurate, factual, and accountable information (Bennett, WL, 2003). As an official institution that is shaded by binding rules, the mainstream media is expected to appear as a counterweight to the widespread reporting on social digital media in the community. For this reason, researchers consider mainstream media to be worthy of being maintained and maintained because the information disseminated is more accountable (Kominfo, 2018; Nugroho, B. & Samsuri, 2013).

The news media today are not monolithic. They are not frozen in a permanent standard set. But they suffer from an innate bias that protects corporate power and consequently weakens the public's ability to understand the forces that create scenes within the state. Bias in favor of the status quo within states, as occurred during the Sacco-Vanzetti case, do not appear to have changed materially over time. When Senator Joseph McCarthy came to power

the pillars of democracy in a country. If studied with the theory of Niche (niche can be interpreted as a niche or space of life). Niche's theory starts from an ecological perspective in seeing competition between media in providing accurate information amidst the New Media disturbances in society (Strate, L., 2004; Bagdikian, BH, 2004). It is like the process of competition between media industries as a process towards the Niching and Networking era to media monology (Nurliah, 2018; Sendjaja, 1996). Looking further at the competition between media, Pavilk (1996) & Deuze, M. (2007) used a competition approach between newspapers as the mainstream media to maintain its position by trying to get sufficient supporting financial sources. Meanwhile, in reality, these supporting sources are limited in number and are being contested by various media which continues to grow in number. Such as Tribun Timur and Harian Fajar in Makassar City as mainstream media in their competition to win the consumer market for readers in the disruptive era of *New Media Technology*.

This study aims to reveal that the mass media as the mainstream media has become one of the important forces of the modern age. The challenges in the revolution in the field of science and technology make the mass media have such a broad spectrum, reaching all regions, layers of society with massive intensity. This study focuses on the problem of how the disruption of *new media technology* in seizing the consumer market for the readers of the Fajar & Tribun Timur newspapers in Makassar City. The benefits of this research can be a reference for mass media companies that are converging to further improve the development of their media platforms, be it print, online, or other platforms so that they can win the competition in the realm of media digitization.

Methods

This study uses a qualitative-exploratory method with a comparative approach to a case study on Fajar & Tribun Timur Daily in Makassar (Creswell & Poth, 2016) as an exploration of *new media technology* in seizing the consumer market for Harian Fajar & Tribun Timur newspaper readers in the city of Makassar and also can be a reference for mass media companies that are converging in order to further enhance the development of their media platforms, both print, and online platforms. The data and facts used are obtained through literature study by studying, reading, studying books, journals, official documents, and other relevant data sources so as to produce the best research. Once obtained, the data is then analyzed and interpreted as developed by Miles, Huberman, & Saldana (2014) with the stages of data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and data verification, to produce conclusions. In the form of new findings that will be useful for readers in seeing the sustainability of the Harian Fajar and Tribun Timur newspaper industries in Makassar City due to the disruption of *New Media*. Then assisted with *tools* Nvivo 12 Pro (Woolf & Silver, 2017) to explore more deeply the problems that occurred and get perfect conclusions.

Results and Discussion

Mass Media Convergence in the New Media Digital Disruption Era

Two mass media in Makassar, Harian Fajar and TribunTimur, adopted new technology in their media management system by establishing an online platform and a special division that handles their online media. From the information from the four informants in the two media, it was obtained that the presence of online media that synergized with other media platforms was very important. The use of online media is an innovation in adopting communication technology that continues to grow. The internet combined with personal computers, laptops, smartphones, PDAs, and Ipods has become an important creation as a news distribution tool other than agents or newspaper deliverymen. The reach of readers is getting wider and more diverse with the addition of distribution tools (Nurliah, 2018; Hasni, et al., 2019).

Tribun Timur, which has minimal Human Resources (HR), uses this new technology to add media forms other than newspapers, without the need to recruit too many workers. The Tribune emphasized that the presence of technology was utilized as much as possible through one newsroom (single newsroom) with many media platforms (multiplatform). The budget can be reduced through minimal workers with maximum work results. Because, one journalist has duties as an online journalist, newspaper journalist, television journalist, and radio journalist. So that the mission of the Tribune with the presence of various forms of media can be realized, namely being able to fulfill the wishes of readers or customers without spending a larger budget (Nurliah, 2018; Hasni, et al., 2019).

Pavlik's research (1996) that the existence of new technology in the mass media to retain viewers while also adding new viewers. This is what the two mass media want to achieve. Even though Fajar's informants are very sure that even though the internet is spreading, it will not interfere with Fajar's circulation. It even tends to rise when there are certain events. However, to a lesser extent, Fajar's online media presence is intended so that competitors do not interfere with readers and especially not interfere with Fajar Group's media business. Meanwhile, the informant from the Tribune frankly stated that the news portal was there to fulfill the wishes of its readers. So do not be surprised if social networking sites are also intensively used to promote their latest news (Nurliah, 2018; Hasni, et al., 2019).

The two media that are the object of this research have converged, namely in addition to distributing media through print media as well as online media where the driving engine is the internet. So in accordance with the theory of Pavlik and Friedman, there is a collaboration and connection between print and electronic media. Various devices have synergized with each other. For this convergence, informants from the Tribun timur emphasized the efficiency and effectiveness of the Tribun timur's work. Honestly, the Tribun timur informants realized that they lacked resources. So, even though they have few human resources, with one newsroom (editor) they can work on many media platforms. Meanwhile, an informant from Fajar emphasized that Fajar's vision is multimedia where all forms of media can be produced by the Fajar Group company, so that like self-service, customers just have to choose what suits their tastes (Nurliah, 2018; Hasni, et al., 2019). The implications of conventional media (newspapers), especially Tribun Timur & Fajar Daily which are integrated with new media (online) can be seen in the table below:

Table 1 Implications of Print Media (newspaper) Tribun Timur & Fajar in the New Media Disruption era

No.	Mass media	Implications
1.	Tribun Timur	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Internet access audiences can choose what news suits their tastes and the information they want because there are entertainment news features, the latest, technology, regional news, and reports from residents. 2. Because the news is presented on a follow-up basis, the accessor can freely choose or read which news first. Because the news index is available as well as hyperlinks with a number of related news. 3. News that has been covered by Tribun Timur journalists can be accessed again if the public wants to access them again. There is a news search engine, an index of past news, and hyperlinks. 4. Any news from any media can be obtained because a number of news sites are linked to the Tribun Timur website. 5. News that is presented per minute because it carries the character of media that is real-time news. Journalists who are in the field have been equipped with photos, smartphones, and laptops so that when an incident occurs, they just need to send it to the Tribun timur uploader. 6. Tribune can make e-radio and e-tv without the need to bring radio and television technology. Only by entering the software into the Tribune news site, the radio and television program features can be enjoyed by the audience accessing the Tribun timur news site while also enjoying the latest news and news versions of the newspaper (e-paper). 7. The news can be responded to by the audience of the Tribun Timur news site. Users can also propose news, cover news, and criticize existing news because there are chat rooms available via Tribune's Facebook, Tribune's Twitter, Tribune's Yahoo Messenger, and Tribune's email.
2.	Harian Fajar	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Access to the Fajar news portal can choose what news suits their taste for information because they already have actual news features, entertainment, technology, and news from the region. 2. Fajar website users can read which news first. Because the news index is available as well as hyperlinks with a number of related news. 3. News that has been covered by Fajar journalists can be accessed again if the public wants to access them again. There is a news search engine, an index of past news, and hyperlinks. 4. Any news from certain media can be obtained because a number of news sites are linked to Fajar's website. 5. The news that is presented is real-time news because the journalists in the field have been equipped with photos, smartphones, and laptops so that when an incident occurs, all they have to do is send it to Fajar's uploader staff. 6. Fajar group has run a multimedia company so that apart from newspapers and the internet, the public can also get information through Fajar TV and Fajar Radio. Fajar News in the internet version can be enjoyed via Fajar PDF. 7. Fajar's interactivity can be done through comments on the news because a column is provided to respond to the news.

Source: Processed from Nurliah (2018), 2022

According to informants from the *Tribun timur*, the presence of online media was very useful and changed their performance. This is also because a more 'networked' digital society presents significant challenges for individuals to push for reform through new technologies (Tapsell, R., 2017). What is certain is that it is easy for journalists to send news and photos quickly through a variety of increasingly sophisticated communication tools. Informants from *Fajar Daily* make it easy for readers or viewers to choose whatever news they like. Just click, the news is already in front of the reader. The existence of this technology answers that only creative people and those who are able to adapt to technology can drive the globalization of the world (Deuze, M., 2007). As previously stated, the informant from *Fajar* emphasized *Fajar's* vision in an effort to compete for the market in *Makassar City* with maximum multimedia, where all forms of media can be produced by *Fajar Group* companies, so that like self-service, customers just have to choose what suits their tastes.

Tribun Timur & Harian Fajar Competition in Mainstream Media Competition in Conquest of Market in Makassar City

In the *Brotherhood's* research (2020) it is stated that print media will indeed still exist, but the level of competition is so tight. The print media industry should strive to penetrate the widest possible market in the hope of increasing market share and advertising. Various strategies were carried out in the form of adaptation and innovation with technological advances. The print media industry must make changes in order to survive in the midst of technological developments that are growing so rapidly. Newspapers must be able to define themselves from the medium. Newspapers should not be conventional with just a piece of paper. In addition, it is also necessary for the print media to present themselves as media that can truly meet the needs of the people who are now more "mobile" in the midst of the presence of online media.

This competition can be explained in niche theory (media ecology) that the media environment is related to the reciprocal relationship between the mass media and its supporting environment. *Harian Fajar* and *Tribun Timur* compete in the same environment because they are local general media that target the same news. So from the content, advertisements, to the audience, readers have the same segment. What distinguishes the ability to create news innovations or rubrics that are unique and interesting so as to bring in readers and advertisers (Nurliah, 2018; Moon & Hadley, 2014). In table 2 below, it is explained about the competition for the mainstream media for the *Tribun Timur & Harian Fajar* in fighting over the market in the city of *Makassar*:

Table 2 Description of the SKH Tribune Timur & Harian Fajar in Fighting for the Market in Makassar City

No.	The Mainstream Media	SWOT
1	Tribun Timur	<p>Strength – Opportunity:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Accommodating the tastes and needs of readers and continuing to innovate by continuously improving the quality of news that is packaged in a comprehensive manner so that it remains accurate. 2. Maintain cooperative relationships that have been established and form partnerships with new stakeholders both with the government and the private sector to participate in organizing events / promotional activities that are carried out regularly to attract communities or hold activities to form communities so that they can increase the level of newspaper readability while strengthening the brand image owned by SKH Fajar. 3. Upgrade production machines/printing machines in order to optimize printing operations both in terms of print time and print quality. 4. Increase the number of agents, for example by giving commissions, making them distributors. 5. The distribution process is carried out faster to customers. Direct sales are carried out by maintaining the continuity of publication and delivery of newspapers, lest customers become disappointed because newspapers are late in the publication or late to customers.
		<p>Weakness – Opportunity:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase the quantity of human resources and conduct training as well as development and regeneration of human resources, considering that the media industry is a creative industry that requires young people with qualified abilities and skills. The addition of human resources is carried out with a strict selection in order to screen for strong and tenacious human resources, then send human resources to participate in various courses according to their fields to increase knowledge. In addition, it is necessary to invite experts in various fields to add insight and human resource capabilities. 2. To increase sales growth, sales promotions can be carried out in the form of promotions directed to new customers, such as samples, coupons, discounts, bundling packages or promotions directed to agents in the form of discounts, dealer contests, or promotions aimed at salesmen, which can be in the form of bonuses. 3. Establish a network with schools and universities where they can participate in news writing at SKH Tribun Timur by providing a special rubric for young journalists from schools and universities both in Makassar and outside Makassar. 4. Expand distribution area. To expand the marketing network so that it becomes a mainstay market, the circulation department must actively develop an agency area that can open up opportunities to sell on a subscription basis. For example, collaborating with the district, sub-district, RT, or RW officials, villages, and other communities and organizations. In addition, the distribution of newspapers is also carried out in the outskirts, villages in Makassar City which have not been targeted. Villages or remote areas have the same information needs as urban communities. For the distribution process, it can run more effectively and efficiently, if the company plans the scheduling and sequences of routes in transportation. Scheduling and determining transportation routes can be completed using the Savings Matrix method. From data processing and discussion of distribution channel problems using the Savings Matrix method, distribution holds an important factor, because, without the right distribution pattern, this process will also cost a lot and result in wastage in terms of time, distance and energy so that circulation needs to constantly evaluate distribution channels. to increase efficiency and effectiveness.

		<p>Strength – Treath:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Selling newspaper package advertisements with seminars or other offers, bundling programs, or sales strategies carried out by combining newspaper sales with giveaways with brands that have collaborated with SKH Tribun Timur. 2. Carry out CSR activities as a form of concern for the surrounding environment, one of the activities that are humanitarian in nature, one of the activities that are humanitarian, such as providing assistance for mobile libraries, donating funds to schools that are still very minimal in facilities, making social activities by helping a social organization will be very influential for the SKH Tribun Timur business brand. Having and building good relationships with the community can increase the prestige of SKH Tribun Timur in the Industrial world, and help sales later. This activity was able to strengthen the brand image of SKH Fajar as a newspaper that not only pursues profit but also cares for humanity.
		<p>Weakness – Treath:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Create activities that people can talk about. Like an interesting competition that can be the subject of people's talk, and can invite people to get involved. The involvement is not only limited to being a buyer, but can also be involved directly through the competition that is carried out. 2. SKH Tribun Timur has moved towards the digital industry and is conducting media convergence with the presence of the news portal, tribun-timur.com so that its human resources are trained to be able to adapt to technological developments in order to increase reader access on the Tribune news portal and in the print media. One thing that can be done is holding quizzes, loading viral content, being active in social media groups, creating fan pages. Marketing HR can also do marketing with email marketing via email SKH Tribun Timur can even get potential buyers via email.
2.	Harian Fajar	<p>Strength – Opportunity:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Accommodating the tastes and needs of readers and continuing to innovate while still improving the quality of news that is packaged in a comprehensive, objective and proportional way so that it remains accurate. 2. Maintain cooperative relationships that have been established and re-establish cooperation with new stakeholders, both with the government and the private sector to participate in organizing events / promotional activities that are carried out regularly to attract communities or hold activities to form communities so as to increase the readability of newspapers while strengthening SKH Fajar's brand image. 3. Upgrade production machines/printing machines so that they can optimize printing operations both in terms of print time and print quality. 4. Expanding the product distribution area to many rural areas in 24 urban districts in South Sulawesi and all areas in Makassar City. Villages or remote areas have the same information needs as urban communities. To strengthen the marketing network so that it becomes a mainstay market, the circulation department must actively develop an agency area that can open up opportunities to sell on a subscription basis. For example, collaborating with sub-district, village, RT, or RW officials, etc.
		<p>Weakness – Opportunity:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase the quantity of human resources and conduct training and human resource development, and regenerate human resources considering that the media industry is a creative industry that requires young people with qualified abilities and skills. 2. Optimizing services to consumers through the presentation of similar news that can be accessed using internet media, news that has just happened can be directly delivered in real-time. 3. The distribution process that is carried out faster to direct sales customers is carried out by maintaining the continuity of the issuance and the provision of delivery. Harian Fajar as much as possible maintains the quality of service by maintaining the speed of newspaper distribution to customers. Do not let the customer become disappointed because the newspaper is late to be published or late to the customer.

		For the distribution process, it can run more effectively and efficiently, if the company plans the scheduling and sequences of transportation routes. Scheduling and determining transportation routes can be completed using the Savings Matrix method. From data processing and discussion of distribution channel problems using the Savings Matrix method. Distribution plays an important factor, because, without the right distribution pattern, this process will also be expensive and result in wastage in terms of time, distance and energy so circulation needs to constantly evaluate distribution channels to improve efficiency and effectiveness.
		<p>Strength – Treath:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Utilizing qualified work facilities and a high level of employee loyalty as well as synergy between divisions to compete with competitors to form the <i>brand image</i> of SKH Fajar. 2. Optimizing the quality of news, by maintaining the accuracy and truth of information, as well as presenting news that inspires, the good news is the good news to attract readers' interest, where online media often prioritizes speed and ignores the truth of the news to get a rating. And the information displayed in online media sometimes has no news value, does not match journalistic values and journalistic methods. 3. Apart from being supported by Fajar online, Harian Fajar is also active on social media to disseminate information, either via Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and other social media. 4. In order to increase the number of agents, you can give commissions, making them distributors.
		<p>Weakness – Treath:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. SKH Fajar has carried out media convergence with the presence of Fajar.com. However, efforts need to be made to increase reader access at Fajar.com, one of which is by holding quizzes, posting viral content, being active in social media groups, and creating fan pages. 2. Conduct a bundling program or a sales strategy that is carried out by combining newspaper sales with giving away with brands that have collaborated with SKH Fajar so that buyers do not hesitate to buy at relatively higher prices because they get more profit.

Source: Processed from Hasni, et al. (2019), 2021

Likewise, with the birth of online media, the battle for the market in the same ecological space is getting sharper and fiercer. Even though Fajar first established online media in 1997, but at that time he had not seriously worked on it. It was only when the Tribun timur intensively promoted their online media presence in 2007, Fajar did not waste time reviving his online media in 2008. Although Fajar said it was not because of following his competitor's media, it can be clearly read that Fajar's online media revival was none other than so that the Tribun Timur is not alone in the world of local digital media (Nurliah, 2018; Hasni, et al., 2019).

Seeing the strategy that the Tribun Timur and Harian Fajar used in utilizing the internet is appropriate if you look at Michael Porter's description of utilizing technology and offering varied products by building online news sites in addition to maintaining the production of print articles (Moon & Hadley, 2014). However, a sustainable competitive advantage can only be done by the Tribun Timur. By outperforming its product offerings above average. The Tribun Timur built a special division for the Tribun-Online. Harian Fajar also does the same thing with a special division but in terms of handling Fajar online news (Nurliah, 2018; Hasni, et al., 2019).

As mentioned by Bennett (2003) the prospect of competing for media power in an era of new media disruption may seem smaller today than ever before. The combination of mainstream media content in the mass media has become a separate problem for the mass media in Makassar City. The trend of mass media in Makassar City is the same as what Bagdikian (2004), McChesney (2016), and Herman & Chomsky (2010) said about the growing media monopoly, government deregulation, the emergence of commercial news and information systems, and corporate norms. which avoids social responsibility beyond the benefits to shareholders. In Makassar City, the mainstream media's efforts are more about selling and offering advertisers with high-cost advertorial content, particularly news on developments, politics, and other ceremonial events (Bennett, 2003, 2016). As stated by Bennett (2016), the reason that local political coverage has become the main news commodity in Makassar, especially during the Pilkada, is because it is formulated based on chaos and personality profiles. The era of technology disruption to the print media of *Tirbun Timur & Harian Fajar* saw it as an opportunity to seize the market by pursuing advertisers and readers by utilizing technology and transforming to a digital news system.

The Strategy of *Tribun Timur & Harian Fajar* in the New Media Destruction Era in Seizing the Readers' Consumer Market in Makassar

Map emerging practices in the media profession such as journalism, advertising, marketing communications, and public relations in adapting to a new global environment, characterized by an increasingly participatory media culture. Among creatives and brand managers in advertising agencies, 'interactive advertising' is at the center of contemporary buzz (Deuze, M., 2007). Markets in the culture industry brainstorm about the potential of upstream marketing, while in public relations opportunities for two-way symmetrical communication are explored. All of these trends are part of the same phenomenon in the convergence of production cultures and in the competition for markets for information consumption. Deuze, M. (2007) sees these developments discussed in terms of their potential impact on consensual assumptions about the nature of media work, viewed through the lens of the combination of individual creativity and mass production, also known as creative industries.

Tapsell (2017) states that media conglomerates tend to develop a digital conglomerate business model that is almost the same, trying to become a multiplatform media company, and to achieve this, they concentrate their news production. This has been shown by CT Corp. Quoting Tapsell (2017), Ishadi SK, then commissioner of CT Corp, said that detik.com was not only used as a Trans Media news center, but also a business center. "To support it,". Trans Corp will build facilities in Jakarta, including 50 TV studios which will become the newsroom centers for all Transmedia companies. This includes hotels, theme parks, ocean parks, and entertainment theaters that will become business centers. According to Tapsell (2017), the business plan of each media company in Indonesia is to capture audiences through as many platforms as possible. They also build a media "ecosystem", from content to communication infrastructure. Thus, according to Tapsell, it will be difficult for new media—especially those based online—to survive and have a sustainable business, if they don't join the conglomerate. Research by Merlyna Lim (2013) and Ignatius Haryanto (2011) shows how the leaders of these companies not only have an influence on the media landscape, but also

their involvement in the Indonesian political and economic stage. Making the quality of journalism is at stake. As also mentioned in Putra's research (2019) on the best adaptation strategy for mass media in dealing with the New Media Technology era of disruption by adapting to consumer behavior as a non-negotiable choice so that the information presented can be enjoyed by many users. The print media industry must be able to adapt to changes in consumer behavior while continuing to innovate business.

If you look at the results of research from Alhas, MH (2010), it shows that 1) the *Tribun timur* as a source of information for the Makassar people is considered capable of meeting all information and news needs. 2) Although the *Tribun timur* is quite complete in presenting information, the audience tends to be more selective in sorting out the information. 3) The *Tribun timur* in the eyes of the public has more value than its competitors. It can be seen from the speed of *Real-Time* updates and the completeness of the information presented. 4) People tend to only know the *Tribun timur* Portal only through the desktop version or in other words, the mobile version of the *Tribun timur* portal is not very familiar to the Makassar people. 5) Differences in the level of need, education, and profession determine the selection of information from each user. 6) In the uses and gratification theory, users don't just stop at online media selection. After selecting online media as a source of information, the user then chooses the type of information that suits his needs. 7) The advantages of the *Tribun timur* online media are also the disadvantages of the *Tribun timur* portal. It is also said that the results of Kartika's research (2016) show that (1) the editorial policy of the *Tribun timur* daily in presenting the National Tribune rubric has special considerations. The basis for considering whether or not a news item is worthy of being published in the National Tribune rubric is that the news must have news value, have closeness, especially to the Sulawesi area, both geographically and emotionally, as well as the most popular news on *Tribunnews.com* and *Kompas.com*. (2) The category of news that is often published in the National Tribune rubric is news about politics and law. From a political perspective, the National Tribune often raises news about the Golkar party because this party is a strong party in Sulawesi, especially in the city of Makassar. From a legal perspective, news from the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) is often published because there are Sulawesi people in the KPK. The implications of this research are: (1) It is hoped that the *Tribun timur* daily will continue to be a forum for the aspirations of the community, especially the Sulawesi area so that the community has a place to continue to express their opinions. (2) To the editorial team, especially in the National Tribune rubric, to remain guided by the editorial policy in selecting the news to be published.

Based on research conducted by Mutmainnah, S. (2016), it shows that the strategies that have been carried out on the *Fajaronline.com* portal are: The strategy is supported by three things, 1) the strategy in selecting issues is made effective in choosing a different angle so that it is not the same as the print. or mostly online media, 2) the issue placement strategy consists of two things, namely important and interesting issues, 3) a news development strategy by combining the concepts of conventional news presentation and follow-up news. And the strategy taken by *Fajaronline.com* editors in maintaining news accuracy related to the speed of online news presentation, namely: 1) journalists are always reminded about the accuracy of their news and recheck news after being sent by journalists and after being edited by the

editor, 2) abbreviating news directly to the core of the news. which is very important, 3) take advantage of shares on social media, 4) provide an assessment of the news sent by journalists with points doubled for popular news.

The view of media observers on online media, especially Fajaronline.com, is that the development of converged media is only an answer to current media developments. Fajaronline.com for a local scale is considered an online media because it is under a trusted big company brand. It's just that Fajaronline.com is advised to make a better pattern and dare to do development. The implication of this research is that Fajaronline.com is expected to continue to provide updated, actual, fast, and reliable news in order to continue to exist and survive. It is better to have a special journalist for online media, readers should be smart consumers in receiving information presented by online media. In Astuti's research, SW (2016) showed that Harian Fajar carried out various strategies and innovations to be able to compete in the digital era. The innovation made by Harian Fajar is a strategy to develop products and increase public trust by providing attractive displays such as graphics, caricatures, and photos. In addition, Harian Fajar also presents a rubric that follows the information needs of readers of various generations by utilizing the company's resources and strengths. The implication of the results of this study is that the media always presents quality news and is able to be justified, and can be useful for readers. Scientific implications for the development of further research to further sharpen sensitivity in seeing media strategies to gain trust from the public.

Tribun Timur & Harian Fajar have anticipated the presence of new media by publishing Tribun-Timur.com & Fajaronline.com, an online version and a digital version in the form of an e-paper. Readers of these two print media partially turn to online news. But at the end of 2019, there was another big change. Facebook and YouTube and Instagram are new references for news and information seekers. This has been exacerbated by the Covid-19 pandemic. So that the transformation of mainstream media such as Tribun Timur & Harian Fajar needs to also transform to social media. The effect is also great. Advertisers turned to Tribun Timur.com and more cooperation was directed to the YouTube Tribune Timur and the Facebook Tribune Timur as well as the Makassar Online News. If initially, the largest source of advertising was from print, now it has shifted to digital. The main challenges are focus and speed. If the print can still wait for the deadline in the middle of the night. So in online and social media, the deadline is every time. Deadlines per issue and per incident. Strengthen social media and online. Educate clients to migrate online. At the same time, educate journalists to get used to working according to the principles of online media and social media. Quick and precise. Educate editors with online working principles, choosing news angles according to online needs and principles (Kambi, 2022).

Conclusion

In the Era of Destruction, *New Media* in Makassar City made efforts to media converge in triggering competition to be able to seize the market, whether advertising or readers. Conventional media are now flocking to build sites, create accounts on social networking sites, to create blogs. This is nothing but an effort to gain a more diverse readership, as well

as increase the financial coffers through advertising in online media. In today's highly competitive environment, advertising in online media is considered more effective with a wider and larger audience reach. Online media, which is more interactive, is more popular as a new marketing medium. This unique feature has become popular among users (users/participants) and advertisers.

Then in a simple conclusion, researchers in the era of new media disruption in seizing the consumer market for Harian Fajar & Tribun Timur newspaper readers in Makassar City: (1) Adding a print platform to online media through online news sites, more or less able to increase the number of readers on conventional media especially newspapers because news distribution no longer only relies on newspapers but also online media; & (2) Observing the competition in the mass media in Makassar, it can be studied using the Niche theory. The presence of online media in these two local media makes the competition between them even sharper. Not only fighting for the same readers, but also fighting over advertisements and making news that is most widely read by the public, both in print and online media. The era of technological disruption to print media, Tirban Timur & Harian Fajar, saw it as an opportunity to seize the market by pursuing advertisers and readers by utilizing Technology and Transformation into digital news systems.

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